

National Leprosy Conference 2025

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Abstract Book

Ministry of Health

Anti-Leprosy Campaign

World Health Organization
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LEPROSY
INITIATIVE

PP-3: Development of a Tool for Investigation of Child Leprosy Cases in Colombo Regional Director of Health Services Area

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Background:

Leprosy in children is a key indicator of ongoing transmission in the community and reflects lapses in early detection and preventive activities. Investigating each child leprosy case in detail is essential to identify the sources of infection, potential risk factors and programmatic gaps. A structured approach would facilitate the uniform application of this activity leading to comprehensive data collection and drawing meaningful conclusions from field investigations.

Description of the intervention/initiative:

A comprehensive child leprosy case investigation tool was developed by the district team, with technical guidance and inputs from the Anti Leprosy Campaign, Ministry of Health. The tool was designed for use by district-level health staff during field visits to child leprosy cases. It aimed to ensure systematic data collection covering clinical details, epidemiological background, environmental factors and social determinants. The format also included sections for documenting household contacts, school environment and preventive measures implemented, thereby facilitating a holistic understanding of each case.

Methods used for the evaluation:

Following development, the tool was implemented in district-level investigations of child leprosy cases. Its use was monitored by the district team in coordination with the Anti Leprosy Campaign. Evaluation focused on assessing the completeness and quality of data captured using the tool, as well as its practicality and usefulness during field investigations. Observations from district team and national-level reviewers were used to assess its effectiveness in standardizing the investigation process. The tool was introduced in the district presentation done in Annual Leprosy Review held on 5th August 2025

Results:

Up to 20th October 8 child case investigations have been done using the developed template. The introduction of the tool improved the uniformity and completeness of child leprosy case investigations at the district level. It enabled the systematic recording of clinical, social and environmental factors and supported identification of possible sources of infection. The tool also enhanced coordination between district teams and the Anti Leprosy Campaign, facilitating more structured reporting and follow-up actions.

Lessons learnt:

Developing and introducing a standardized tool for child leprosy case investigation strengthened surveillance and response mechanisms at the district level. Technical collaboration with the Anti Leprosy Campaign ensured that the tool was comprehensive and programmatically relevant. Future updates based on field experience will further enhance its usefulness and contribute to improved understanding and control of leprosy transmission among children.